

UNBALANCED CROSS-PLIED ELLIPTIC PLATES

UNDER UNIFORM PRESSURE*

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Unbalanced cross-ply laminated elliptic plates with bending membrane coupling are analyzed for constant uniform pressure load. Closed form polynomial solutions are presented for the clamped bending boundary conditions and two cases of mixed membrane boundary conditions. In the first case the tangential displacement and the normal load integral and in the second case the normal displacement and the shear load integral vanish on the ellipse boundary. Numerical comparisons are presented with exact and approximate solutions for other membrane boundary conditions for composite plates of glass, Thorneil and boron fibers in epoxy matrices. Circular plates are included as a special case. It is shown that the membrane boundary conditions play a minor role in the displacement predictions for the circular and elliptic plates studied.

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Introduction

Applications of high performance laminated composites result in a very few plies when the total weight is an important consideration. The small number of plies limits the possible elastically balanced combinations where the laminate is elastically symmetric about the midsection. Hence the analyst must, of necessity, consider the unbalanced laminate constructions. Advances in fabrication techniques of unbalanced laminates show that the thermal warpage is eliminated by curing the elastically balanced subsets and subsequently laminating the subsets at room temperatures. This makes the analysis of such structures important to ensure the structural integrity under various load conditions. In addition to the difficulties associated with the determination of 'buckling' loads for unbalanced structures, many questions surround the selection of appropriate membrane boundary conditions for the analysis of simple static structures. For this reason, an investigation of the membrane boundary conditions was undertaken for unbalanced elliptic plates under uniform normal pressure. This work describes the results of this investigation. The elliptic plates analyzed are unbalanced laminates consisting of two unidirectional layers as shown in Figure 1. One layer is oriented along the major axis of the ellipse while the other is perpendicular to the first along the minor axis. The effect of skewing these axes has not been examined. For the circular plate it is only required that the unidirectional layers be perpendicular to each other.

Fig. 1: Elliptic Plate Stiffening Configuration, Tangential and Normal Directions.

Analytical Formulation and Solution

For the laminated construction specified, the resultant forces and moments can be specified as functions of membrane strains and changes in bending curvature using the Hooke's Law as follows{1}*.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & B_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & 0 & 0 & B_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{66} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ B_{11} & 0 & 0 & D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & B_{22} & 0 & D_{21} & D_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_{xy} \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

or in abbreviated form as,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The strains and curvatures can be expressed in terms of displacements through the Love-Kirchhoff assumptions of the small displacement theory.

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \epsilon_y &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} & \epsilon_{xy} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \\ \kappa_x &= -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} & \kappa_y &= -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} & \kappa_{xy} &= -2\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The force equilibrium equations for flat structural elements are,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial y} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial N_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial N_y}{\partial y} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial^2 M_x}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 M_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial^2 M_y}{\partial y^2} + q &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where q is the lateral load and the transverse shear forces Q_{xz} and Q_{yz} have been eliminated.

Substituting the Hooke's Law expressions of Eq.(1) into the equilibrium Eq.(4) and using the kinematic Eq.(3) of small deformations, the following three equilibrium equations in terms of displacements are obtained,

* Numbers in parentheses designate references listed at the end

$$A_{11} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + A_{66} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + (A_{12} + A_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial y} - B_{11} \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x^3} = 0$$

$$(A_{21} + A_{66}) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} + A_{66} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + A_{22} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} - B_{22} \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial y^3} = 0$$

$$D_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} - B_{11} \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^3} - B_{22} \frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial y^3} = q \quad (5)$$

Considering the ellipse boundary as shown in Figure 1, the normal and tangential boundary displacements can be written in terms of Cartesian displacements as,

$$u_n = u \cos \theta + v \sin \theta$$

$$u_t = -u \sin \theta + v \cos \theta \quad (6)$$

Using a second order transformation, the normal and shear loads can be expressed as,

$$N_n = N_x \cos^2 \theta + N_y \sin^2 \theta + 2 N_{xy} \sin \theta \cos \theta$$

$$N_t = (N_y - N_x) \sin \theta \cos \theta + N_{xy} (\cos^2 \theta - \sin^2 \theta) \quad (7)$$

If the ellipse boundary ∂B is expressed as,

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{then on the boundary, } \cot \theta = xb^2/ya^2 \quad (9)$$

Closed form polynomial solutions have been obtained for balanced orthotropic{2,3} and anisotropic {4} elliptic plates with boundaries clamped in bending. For such plates $B_{11} = B_{22} = 0$ and the equilibrium Eq.(5) are uncoupled for bending response w and membrane responses u and v . Consequently the bending response can be solved for without specifying the membrane boundary conditions. Closed form polynomial solutions have also been obtained for the unbalanced elliptic plate under consideration {5} for the 'unmixed' membrane boundary conditions such that either the boundary displacements or the boundary force components vanish along the normal and tangential directions to the ellipse boundary.

In this work solutions for two 'mixed' cases of membrane boundary conditions will be presented.

$$\text{Case C1: } u_n = 0 \quad : \text{ zero normal boundary displacement} \quad (10)$$

$$\int_{\partial B} N_t ds = 0 \quad : \text{ zero sum for boundary shear forces} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Case C2: } u_t = 0 \quad : \text{ zero tangential boundary displacement} \quad (12)$$

$$\int_{\partial B} N_n = 0 \quad : \text{ zero sum for boundary normal forces} \quad (13)$$

Clamped bending boundary conditions are assumed for both cases such that on the ellipse boundary,

$$w = \frac{\partial w}{\partial n} = 0 \quad (14)$$

CASE C1: The following polynomial expressions for displacements satisfy the membrane boundary condition of Eq.(10).

$$\begin{aligned} u &= x \left[u_1 \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} \right) + u_2 \frac{y^2}{b^2} \right] \\ v &= y \left[v_1 \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} \right) - u_2 \frac{x^2}{a^2} \right] \\ w &= w_0 \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} \right)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Satisfaction of the boundary condition of Eq.(11) leads to the following algebraic relation among the four constants,

$$r_1 u_1 + r_2 u_2 + r_3 v_1 + r_4 w_0 = 0 \quad (16)$$

where due to the symmetry of the shear force N_x , the integral of Eq.(11) is taken over the quarter ellipse boundary in the positive quadrant and the constants are as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= 2A_{66}(a-b)(a^2 + 3ab + b^2)/b^2 + 2(2a+b)(A_{11} - A_{12}) \\ r_2 &= 3(a+b)(A_{12} - A_{11}) - 2A_{66}(a^2 - b^2)(a-b)(a^2 + 3ab + b^2)/a^2 b^2 \\ r_3 &= 2A_{66}(a-b)(a^2 + 3ab + b^2)/a^2 + 2(a+2b)(A_{12} - A_{22}) \\ r_4 &= 8B_{11}(2a+b)/a^2 - 8B_{22}(a+2b)/b^2 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The polynomial expressions for displacement from Eq.(15) reduce the partial differential equations of equilibrium Eq.(5) to a set of three algebraic equations. These can be combined with Eq.(16) to yield a 4x4 matrix equation to determine the four unknown coefficients u_1 , u_2 , v_1 and w_0 .

$$\begin{bmatrix} n_{11} & n_{12} & n_{13} & n_{14} \\ n_{21} & n_{22} & n_{23} & n_{24} \\ n_{31} & n_{32} & n_{33} & 0 \\ r_1 & r_3 & r_4 & r_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \\ w_0 \\ u_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ q \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

the matrix coefficients are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} n_{11} &= 6A_{11}/a^2 + 2A_{66}/b^2, & n_{12} &= 2(A_{12} + A_{66})/a^2, & n_{13} &= 24B_{11}/a^4 \\ n_{14} &= 2(A_{12} + A_{66})/a^2 - 2A_{66}/b^2, & n_{21} &= 2(A_{21} + A_{66})/b^2, & n_{22} &= 6A_{22}/b^2 + 2A_{66}/a^2 \\ n_{23} &= 24B_{22}/b^4, & n_{24} &= 2A_{66}/a^2 - 2(A_{21} + A_{66})/b^2, & n_{31} &= 6B_{11}/a^2 \\ n_{32} &= 6B_{22}/b^2, & n_{33} &= 24D_{11}/a^4 + 16(D_{12} + 2D_{66})/a^2 b^2 + 24D_{22}/b^4 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

CASE C2: The displacements are taken as polynomials,

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &= x \left[u_1 \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} \right) + \frac{u_2}{a^2} \right] \\
 v &= y \left[v_1 \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} \right) + \frac{v_2}{b^2} \right] \\
 w &= w_0 \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} \right)^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

These expressions satisfy the membrane boundary conditions of Eq.(12) and substitution into the membrane boundary condition of Eq.(13) leads to the following algebraic relation, where again the integral is taken over the quarter ellipse boundary in the positive quadrant,

$$P_0 u_2 = P_1 u_1 + P_2 v_1 + P_3 w_0 \tag{21}$$

The coefficients are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_0 &= \frac{b^2}{a^2} A_{11} C_2 + \frac{a^2}{b^2} A_{22} S_2 + A_{12} S_0 \\
 P_1 &= 2b^2 A_{11} C_4 + 2a^2 (A_{21} + 2A_{66}) (C_2 - C_4) \\
 P_2 &= 2a^2 A_{22} S_4 + 2b^2 (A_{12} + 2A_{66}) (S_2 - S_4) \\
 P_3 &= \frac{b^2}{a^2} B_{11} C_4 + \frac{a^2}{b^2} B_{22} S_4
 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

C_i and S_i are the definite integrals,

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_i &= \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\cos^i \phi d\phi}{(a^2 \sin^2 \phi + b^2 \cos^2 \phi)^{1/2}} \\
 S_i &= \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\sin^i \phi d\phi}{(a^2 \sin^2 \phi + b^2 \cos^2 \phi)^{1/2}} \quad (i=0,2,4)
 \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

Substitutions of the displacement expressions from Eq.(20) into the equilibrium equations Eq.(5) yield a set of three algebraic equations to determine u_1 , v_1 and w_0 as follows,

$$\begin{bmatrix} n_{11} & n_{12} & n_{13} \\ n_{21} & n_{22} & n_{23} \\ n_{31} & n_{32} & n_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \\ w_0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ q \end{Bmatrix} \tag{24}$$

where the matrix elements n 's are given by Eq.(19). This equation in conjunction with Eq.(21) determines the four unknowns u_1 , v_1 , w_0 and u_2 .

Numerical Results and Discussion

The numerical results are presented for a circular and an elliptic plate for glass-epoxy, Thornel*-epoxy and boron-epoxy composites. Same geometry and thicknesses are used as in {5} for easy comparisons and to demonstrate the effect of membrane boundary conditions. The plates have plies oriented at 0^0 to the major axis of the ellipse on one side of the reference surface and an equal number of plies oriented at 90^0 to the major axis of the ellipse on the other side of the reference surface. Each plate is .080 inches thick with the semi-major axis being twice the semi-minor axis for the elliptic planform. The glass and Thornel plates have four plies on each side of the reference surface while the boron plate has eight. The properties for plies are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Ply Properties{5}

	<u>Glass-Epoxy</u>	<u>Thornel-Epoxy</u>	<u>Boron-Epoxy</u>
E_{11} (psi)	6.7×10^6	25.3×10^6	30.0×10^6
E_{22} (psi)	2.5×10^6	1.2×10^6	3.0×10^6
G_{12} (psi)	1.0×10^6	0.65×10^6	1.0×10^6
ν_{12}	0.25	0.31	0.22
Thickness (inches)	.010	.010	.005

Table 2 lists the numerical coefficients for the out-of-plane displacement w_0 at the center of the plate $x=y=0$. First two lines give the results for the cases C1 and C2 solved for in this work. Next the solution marked 'coupling neglected' is presented and is obtained by completely ignoring the effects of the unsymmetrical laminations. Since the coupling is ignored at the outset, there is no need to specify the membrane boundary conditions. These results are obtained by setting the coupling terms $B_{11}=B_{22}=0$. These results indicate the plate is too stiff. Similar results were found for rectangular plates by Whitney{1}. The next two lines in Table 2 give the results for the free ($N_t=N_n=0$) membrane boundary condition. The approximate method result is obtained by neglecting the coupling term in the reduced stiffness matrix{6,7}. The last line gives the results for the clamped membrane boundary conditions $u_t=u_n=0$. It should be noted that this case is exactly similar to the Case C2ⁿ as the identical equations result for the solution of u_1 , v_1 and w_0 . The presence of the linear term with coefficient u_2 only effects the membrane displacement distributions u and v .

Conclusions

1. The approximate solution method of Reissner and Stavsky{6} and Ashton{7} is applicable to circular and elliptic plates with bending membrane coupling for all membrane boundary conditions considered.
2. For the circular and elliptic planform studied, the selection of membrane boundary condition plays a minor role in the displacement predictions.

* Thornel is a trade mark of Union Carbide Corporation

Table 2 Listing of k values, where $w_0=k(qa^4/1000)$

	Circular Plate a=b			Elliptic Plate a=2b		
Solution Method	Glass-Epoxy	Thornel-Epoxy	Boron-Epoxy	Glass-Epoxy	Thornel-Epoxy	Boron-Epoxy
Case C1	.1015	.0883	.0541	.0132	.0109	.0067
Case C2	.1013	.0882	.0541	.0131	.0109	.0067
coupling neglected	.0874	.0352	.0280	.0112	.0042	.0034
Free-membrane						
Exact {5}	.1016	.0889	.0541	.0132	.0087	.0067
Approx. {6,7}	.1016	.0889	.0541	.0132	.0087	.0067
Clamped-membrane						
Exact {5}	.1009	.0888	.0538	.0131	.0087	.0065

Nomenclature

a,b	semi-major & semi-minor axes of the elliptic plate
A	membrane stiffness matrix
B	coupling stiffness matrix
D	flexural stiffness matrix
A ₁₁ ,...	elements of A matrix
B ₁₁ ,...	elements of B matrix
D ₁₁ ,...	elements of D matrix
C _i	definite integral defined by Eq.(23)
k	coefficient for center deflection
n	normal to the boundary
n ₁₁ ,...	constants defined by Eq.(19)
N	Plate stress resultant vector
N _n ,N _t	normal & tangential components of N
N _x ,N _y ,N _{xy}	normal & shear components of N
M	plate moment resultant vector
M _x ,M _y ,M _{xy}	normal & twist components of M
q	normal pressure load on plate along z axis
Q _{xz} ,Q _{yz}	transverse shear loads
P ₀ ,P ₁ ,P ₂ ,P ₃	plate constants defined by Eq.(22)
r ₁ ,r ₂ ,r ₃ ,r ₄	plate constants defined by Eq.(17)

S_i	definite integral defined by Eq.(23)
u, v	x and y displacements respectively
u_n, u_t	normal & tangential direction displacements
w	displacement along z axis
w_0	plate center displacement along z axis
u_1, u_2, v_1	coefficients for displacements u and v
∂B	plate boundary
ϵ	membrane strain vector
$\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \epsilon_{xy}$	normal and shear components of strain vector
κ	bending curvature vector
$\kappa_x, \kappa_y, \kappa_{xy}$	normal and twist curvatures
θ	angle of the normal n with the x axis
ϕ	angular position on the boundary with respect to x axis

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